

Gold estimation in low grade deposits : example from Penakacherla greenstone terrane

C. Manikyamba

National Geophysical Research Institute (Council of Scientific and Industrial Research), Uppal Road, Hyderabad-500 606, India

E-mail : cmaningri@gmail.com

Abstract : Dharwar craton hosts rich mineral wealth which includes Fe, Mn, Au and diamond occurrences. The banded iron and manganese formations (BIFs and BMFs) are the backbone of iron and manganese industry. Gold is present in mafic-felsic volcanics and associated quartz veins at Penakacherla greenstone belt. The continuous exploration efforts from the last few decades by various organizations in different greenstone belts have established the potential occurrence of low grade deposits. A prominent transcratonic shear zone passes from Ramagiri-Penakacherla-Hungund on which, large number of old workings for gold are situated, indicative of ancient mining activity. Trench samples have been collected from the Badrampalli abandoned mine area of Penakacherla belt. Gold has been analyzed by cyanidation, MIBK and fire assay methods. In all these procedures, Au concentration has indicated its general trend but not exactly in accordance with each other due to its refractory nature and uneven distribution. Gold is present within the pyrite and also as native form. The gold mineralization at Penakacherla belt provides an opportunity to study the multi channel plumbing system and composite alteration zone. The impact of high fluid permeation due to shear zone activity resulted in sericitization, carbonation, sulfidation, silicification and chloritization. The high fluid/rock ratio has influenced different constituents of the host rock. The variable concentrations of gold in this part of shear zone needs suitable extraction procedures for its proper recovery.

Keywords : Gold, greenstone, estimation.

Introduction

The origin and spatio-temporal distribution of gold mineralization in accretionary orogenic provinces are controlled by shear zone activity and fluid infiltration processes¹⁻³. The southern Peninsular India offers a unique insight into many aspects of Precambrian geology, crustal evolution and metallogeny. The area south of Deccan traps and north of southern granulite terrane (SGT) and bordered in the east and west by the Eastern Ghat Mobile Belt (EGMB) and west coast forms the Dharwar craton (DC) in which the greenstone belts cover an area of 37,679 km² that provides an important and favourable lithological and stratigraphic milieu for the remobilization and deposition of gold^{4,5}. In the Dharwar craton, the earliest magmatic event recorded ~3.4 Ga followed by 3.2-2.7 Ga by the eruption of mafic-ultramafic and granitic magmatism and subsequent cratonization. The DC is divided into western (WDC) and eastern (EDC) sectors by the emplacement of 2.5 Ga Closepet granite. There are geological, geophysical and geochemical differences

between these two sectors which appear to reflect on their varied geotectonic environment. Comparatively older rocks (3.4 Ga) are preserved in the western sector of Dharwar craton whereas in the eastern sector, continental crustal growth continued (upto ~2.5 Ga) which is evidenced by the presence of abundant calc-alkaline magmatism in the greenstone belt lithologies of EDC^{6,7}. Dharwar craton is rich in mineral wealth which includes Fe, Mn, Au and diamond occurrences. The initiation of organic activity has been preserved in the western sector in the form of banded iron and banded manganese formations (BIFs and BMFs) that are associated with stromatolites and serve as potential source of iron and manganese. Gold is present in mafic-felsic volcanics and associated quartz veins along with sulphide facies banded iron formations. Though gold has been mined and being mined from Kolar and Hutti belts, the gold potential of Dharwar craton is very low compared to China, South Africa, Australia and Canadian provinces^{8,9} (Groves *et al.*, 2003, 2005). The continuous exploration efforts from the last few years by various organizations in different greenstone belts have

established low grade deposits. There are old workings and abandoned mines in many greenstone belts of Dharwar craton indicative of ancient mining activity. These low grade gold reserves have to be established with efficient exploration and economically viable exploitation strategies¹⁰⁻¹².

In the Dharwar craton, southern India, six major arcuate auriferous greenstone belts with trans-cratonic shears have been identified (Fig. 1). Penakacherla greenstone belt is situated in the central part of the shear zone passing from Ramagiri (in the south) to Hungund (in the north). There are a number of old workings present all along this shear zone. Apart from them, at Penakacherla itself, abandoned Badrampalli old workings are present. Most of the geochemical and isotopic data is available on gaint gold deposits where quartz veins are very thick and contain more than 5 g/ton gold. In these deposits, alteration envelopes have been studied which have established certain parameters. But there is another class of gold deposit with close spaced thin quartz veins having high quartz vein/host rock ratios in which gold is generally found as

highly disseminated from and these are lower grade. These deposits are having high fluid/host rock ratio, but permeation channels are not available or Fe is not sufficient to convert gold of hydrothermal fluids into large deposits of higher concentrations. The gold mineralization at Penakacherla provides an opportunity to study the multi channel plumbing system and composite alteration zone. Here, the impact of high fluid permeation resulted in sericization, carbonation, sulfidation, silicification and chloritization. The high fluid/host rock ratio has influenced different constituents of the host rock^{11,12}.

Gold exploration is hazardous due to its randomly and non uniform distribution style. It is found as free gold with extremely variable size; refractory gold in sub-micron size locked in several sulphides such as pyrite, arsenopyrite or forms complex with tellurium. The uneven distribution of gold especially in low grade deposits makes its exploration much more difficult. It is very difficult to determine that how much quantity should be subjected to analytical procedure. Nugget effect either results in very higher values or in very low values. Higher values result

Fig. 1. Geological map showing major arcuate auriferous greenstone belts in the Dharwar craton of southern peninsular India.

in over estimation of a deposit while lower values result in its underestimation and condemning the deposit. The type of gold and its grain size also makes it a challenging task for an analytical chemist. If 250 g of 100 mesh ore powder containing extremely fine grained gold is subjected to cyanidation, the results are generally low. Chemical dissolution of gold from larger size of sample (50 g) is problematic due to large amount of acid consumption and uncertainties of the extent of dissolution. The use of Knelson concentrator has been advocated to concentrate gold from larger amount of sample (50 kg). But this is effective only when it is quartz-gold ore. In other type of deposits where lots of other heavy minerals are present, fine grained gold will be washed away in the tailings. This results in erroneous errors. Therefore, most of the gold exploration techniques provide a trend of distribu-

tion of gold if large quantity of gold and large number of samples are analysed. Sometimes different analytical procedures for gold estimation in the samples will lead to complex situation. This paper, presents analytical review obtained for the gold concentration of different samples from Penakacherla belt by using different analytical techniques.

Penakacherla greenstone belt :

From Ramgiri to Hungund, ~400 km long shear zone is found in which several old workings for gold are present. Penakacherla part of this shear zone consists mainly of amphibolites and metamorphosed felsic volcanic rocks. The auriferous shear zone passes through the center of the belt (Fig. 2). The proximal zone of shear zone system contains bleached basic phyllonites whereas the distal zone contains amphibolites in which at certain places pillow

Fig. 2. Simplified geological map of Penakacherla greenstone belt showing the shear zone passing through the centre of the belt where old workings for gold are situated near the Bhadrampalli abandoned gold mines.

structures are preserved. Thin bands of BIFs are also found. Axial plane schistosity parallel to F1 fold is the major structure on which the shear zone is superimposed. In the proximal zone, the thickness of the quartz-carbonate veins varies from few mm to few cm and their propagation has taken place mainly along the shear and schistosity planes. Gold and sulfide mineralization is accompanied by silica and carbon within the phyllonite layers along with associated quartz veins (Fig. 3). Due to this factor, a composite alteration envelope is developed and individual alteration envelope across the minute quartz grains cannot be studied separately. This leads to entirely different geochemical paradox of HFSE and REE distribution patterns^{11,12}. This composite shear zone is 50–100 m wide but the central part where the gold mineralization occurs is around 3 m wide. Sampling has been

carried out across the shear zone at different profiles and trenches.

Sampling and analytical techniques :

Since the shear zone is almost N-S direction, 50 kg sample was collected by scrapping the trenches (50 m long and 0.5 m wide) from the wall and bottom. These samples were powdered to 100 mesh and subjected for gold estimation by the procedures namely cyanidation and MIBK analysis by AAS. Out of these, two batches of samples, each containing six and seventeen samples were sent for fire assay analysis at Chitradurga and Gadag fire assay laboratories respectively. The studied samples were subjected to Knelson concentrator separation. The concentrates were analysed by fire assay and MIBK methods of analysis.

The fire assay is the preferred method of determining the mineral grading in a deposit because it is the most accurate method. The fire assay technique uses high temperature and flux to 'melt' the rock and allow the gold to be collected. Lead formed from the reduction of litharge (PbO), is traditionally used as the collecting medium for silver and gold. For fire assaying ores, usually fluxes, materials such as borax, soda, silica are added to the ore. The amounts of each chemical added to the flux mixture depend upon the elements present in the particular ore, such as sulfur and iron. Usually lead, in the form of Litharge (PbO), is also added. The fluxes (except for the lead, which is added for oxidization and sodium carbonate, which is added for de-sulfurization), are added for the purpose of lowering the melting point and imparting a homogeneous fluidity to the melted oxide impurities. The test sample is intimately mixed with a suitable flux that will fuse at high temperature (1050 °C) with the gangue minerals present in the sample to produce a slag that is liquid at the fusion temperature. The liberated precious metals are scavenged by the molten lead and gravitate to the bottom of the fusion crucible. Upon cooling, the lead button is separated from the slag and processed in a separate furnace for a high temperature oxidation (cupellation) where the lead is removed, leaving the precious metals behind as a metallic bead called a prill. The prill can be dissolved in a mixture of hydrochloric and nitric acid (aqua regia) and the concentration determined by spectroscopic methods.

Fig. 3. Field photographs showing the (A) phyllonite outcrop showing intense folding, (B) folded quartz within the phyllonite and (C) secondary quartz and iron minerals within the phyllonite.

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Gold concentrations in trench samples from Penakacherla greenstone belt analysed by different methods are given in Table 1 and precision and accuracy of the analysis by MIBK method are referred to Balaram *et al.*¹³.

Table-1 (contd.)

Table 1. Gold concentrations from the trench samples of Penakacherla greenstone belt (g/ton) analysed by using different analytical methods

Sample No.	CY	MIBK	Fire assay		
			NGRI	Chitra*	Gadag**
MPT-1	1.8	3.05	6.4	3.4	1.4
MPT-2	2.1	2.6	6.4		0.6
MPT-3	0.9	1.12	6		
MPT-4	0.8	0.46	0.8		
MPT-5	0.8	0.51	2.2		
MPT-6	0.9	0.44	0.8		
MPT-7	0.3	0.45	2.6		
MPT-8	0.5	0.4	0.8		
MPT-9	0.5	0.43			
MPT-10	0.4	0.5	1.4		
MPT-11	0.3	0.5	0.2		
MPT-12	0.4	0.48	0.6		
MPT-13	0.5	0.6	2		
MPT-14	0.6	0.49	0.8		
MPT-15	0.4	0.66	1.4		
MPT-16	0.4	1.46	0.2	1.2	1
MPT-17	0.8	0.35	0.2		
MPT-18	0.7	0.5	0.4		
MPT-19	0.4	0.6	0.2		
MPT-20	0.6	0.63	2		
MPT-21	0.6	0.48			
MPT-22	0.3	0.5	0.2		
MPT-23	0.3	0.5	1.4		
MPT-24	0.3	0.57	0.2		
MPT-25	0.4	0.57	1.2		
MPT-26	0.3	0.5	2.6		
MPT-27	0.5	1.2	2		0.4
MPT-28	0.4	0.93	2.6		0.4
MPT-30	0.3	0.52	2		
MPT-31	0.3	0.13	1.5		0.4
MPT-32	0.1	0.12			0.2
MPT-33	0.2	1.19	23.8		0.2
MPT-34	0.1	0.5	13.5		
MPT-35	0.3	0.16	2.2		
MPT-36	0.5	0.01	3.2		
MPT-37	0.4	0.62	0.4		
MPT-38		0.66	8.4		

MPT-39	0.3	0.8	5.6		
MPT-40	1	3.7	15	4.6	4
MPT-41	1.15	2.85	18	3.6	1.2
MPT-42	0.15	0.33	5.6		
MPT-43	0.4	0.03	7		
MPT-44	0.2	0.54	6		
MPT-45	0.8	0.88	15.2		
MPT-46	1.1	4	42		1.2
MPT-47	0.2	1.15	8.8		0.5
MPT-48	0.5		1.8		
MPT-49	1.2	1.81	14.6		0.4
MPT-50	0.9	1.01	8		
MPT-51	2.15	0.03		1	0.2
MPT-52	1.4	0.94	0.4		
MPT-53	0.4	1.15	10.4		0.2
MPT-54	0.5	1.33	0.9		0.1
MPT-55	0.4	1.04	3.6		
MPT-56	0.3	1.26	2		
MPT-57	0.6	0.53		1.6	0.1
MPT-58	0.5	0.64	0.8		
MPT-59	0.4	0.91	1.2		
MPT-60	0.4	0.61	2.6		

*and ** are check 1 and 2 at different laboratories.

CY = Cyanadation; MIBK = Methyl isobutyl ketone; NGRI = Natioanl Geophysical Research Institute fire assay laboratory; Chitra=Chitradurga fire assay laboratory; Gadag = Gadag fire assay laboratory.

Knelson concentrator :

In this process, 10 kg sample has been mixed with water and made as slurry. Then the slurry was introduced into the concentrator cone of Knelson concentrator. When slurry reaches the bottom of the cone, it is forced outward and upward of the cone wall under the influence of centrifugal force. High specific gravity particles are captured and retained in the concentrating cone.

Cyanidation :

200 g of the sample has been subjected to cyanidation process in which the sample is roasted at 650 °C with NH₄NO₃ for one hour to break the sulphides and release gold. Then CaCO₃ is mixed with the sample to maintain pH. This sample has been mixed with water and 2% NaCN solution. Then 25 ml of H₂O₂ is added to the contents with vigorous shaking. The whole mixer has been subjected for air agitation for 24 h. In between every 6 h

NaCN solution was added to avoid the sample evaporation. After 24 h, the contents were filtered and the residue was discarded. 2 g of lead acetate was added to the filtrate and kept on hot plate for 20 m. Then 2 g of zinc dust has been added. After 15 min, 20 ml concentrated HCl has been added with slow stirring. Then a black spongy mass forms. The spongy mass was separated through filtration. After washing and squeezing the water from the spongy mass, it was kept in the lead foil along with 0.1 g silver. Then the foil was kept in a bone ash crucible and put it in the muffle furnace at 1000 °C for ½ hour resulting in bead formation. The bead has been dissolved in dilute HNO₃ to remove silver. Gold was separated and weighed.

MIBK (Methyl Isobutyl Ketone) solvent extraction method :

10 g of roasted sample has been added with 30 ml aqua regia. NaCN has been added to maintain the pH. Heated the mixture with lid for half an hour and removed the lids and left it till the sample evaporated to dryness. Again aqua regia was added and heated till it formed as a pasty layer. Then 40 ml of 3 M HCl was added to the warm, solution. After cooling it was filtered and taken in a separating funnel with 10 ml of equilibrated MIBK. After shaking the entire solution for 3–5 m, organic phase is preserved leaving the aqueous phase. The organic phase is separated in test tube and estimated for gold by Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer along with blank and other standards.

Results

The trench samples of Penakacherla greenstone belt have variable concentrations of gold as determined by different analytical procedures. Cyanidation process yields 0.1–2.15 g/tonne gold while MIBK method gives 0.03–3.7 g/tonne Au in the studied samples (Table 1). Gold concentrations analysed by fire assay method at National Geophysical Research Institute (NGRI), Hyderabad range from 0.2–23.8 g/tonne and these values have been cross checked with the values obtained from the fire assay laboratories at Chitradurga and Gadag.

Discussion

Much is known about the geology of the Archean greenstone belts of Dharwar craton including economic re-

sources. Still there are many unanswered questions regarding the evolutionary aspects of the continental crust and its relation to the mineralization. It is largely believed that greenstone hosted quartz-carbonate vein deposits are related to metamorphic fluids from accretionary processes and generated by prograde metamorphism and thermal re-equilibrium of subducted volcano-sedimentary terranes. The deep seated, Au transporting metamorphic fluid has been channeled to higher crustal levels through major crustal faults or deformation zones. Along its pathway, the fluid dissolves various components, notably gold from volcano-sedimentary packages which will then precipitate as vein material or wall rock replacement in second or third order structures at higher crustal levels through fluid pressure, temperature, pH and other physico-chemical variations¹¹. The underlying solution chemistry that enable the geochemical feat is that though gold is relatively unreactive and gold compounds are generally not very stable, gold has been shown to dissolve in aqueous fluids by forming Au-Cl or Au-S complexes¹⁴. Au-Carbonyl and Au-Te complexes have also been suggested for the dissolution of gold from rocks. Loucks and Maurogenes¹⁵ identified the aqueous gold complex likely to be responsible for the dissolution as AuHs (H₂S)₃⁰ which is consistent with gold characteristics and the natural association of gold with pyrite (FeS₂).

It can be observed through the obtained data that the gold values from different procedures does not exactly tally with each other and provide a trend and indication that this is a region where gold mining may be economically viable. Since cyanidation is a process which brings free gold into solution, in a strongly oxygenated environment. The cyanidation values are the minimum of the gold present in the samples listed in table. The aqua regia dissolution technique for the MIBK procedure attacks both free gold and refractory gold. Therefore, these values are higher than those of cyanidation. But this increase is not proportional because of the presence of gold in different forms. Furthermore, since only 10 g is taken for the aqua regia dissolution, sometimes the MIBK values are less than that of cyanidation. However, by and large in most of the samples, MIBK values either somewhat similar to those of cyanidation or higher to it. This discrepancy has been confirmed by fire assay results of MPT-1 where MIBK value is 3 ppm and fire assay value is 3.4 ppm.

Similarly, in MPT-40 while cyanidation has yielded only 1 ppm; MIBK gave 3.7 and fire assay values are 4 and 4.6 ppm. Knelson concentrator has been considered as a very effective way of separating gold from the host rock. On laboratory scale, this experiment has not been very successful in cases where gold is submicron size and associated sticking to the chloritic and micaceous flakes. Few samples were tested and their results are given in Table 1. 10 kg of the samples MPT-1, 38, 39, 40, 41 and 54 were run through Knelson concentrator and 150–200 g concentrate was collected which have been analysed by fire assay and MIBK. These values are less than the values obtained by MIBK whole rock sample analysis. The overall values from the analysis of the samples of 100 g are high confirming the auriferous nature of the shear zone but the gravity separation could not take place due to the fine grained nature of the gold and presence of the heavy minerals such as magnetite, ilmenite etc.

Penakacherla gold ore contains pyrite, chalcopyrite, arsenopyrite and galena. However, their amount is negligible which is reflected in the abundance of Pb (11.2 ppm), Zn (113 ppm) and Cu (198 ppm). Since the host rock is basic volcanic rock, Co (30 ppm) and Ni (84 ppm) concentrations are consistent with the basic rock^{11,12}. This data indicate that the conventional pathfinder elements (As, Sb, W, Mo, Hg etc.) sometimes do not give the real picture and gold itself is the pathfinder in lode gold deposits.

It is observed that the thermotectonic processes operating on a suitable lithology generate hydrothermal fluids and transcratonic shear zones to produce gold deposits where metamorphism is within 200–350 °C and 2–4 kb pressure. In these conditions the basaltic rocks sweat out the hydrothermal solutes rich in Incompatible Silicate rich Fluids (IRS fluids). Soon after this metamorphism, if a shear zone penetrating deeper level of the crust is formed, it becomes a channel through which these fluids migrate to suitable structures and lithologies where chemical reaction between the rock type and fluids takes place. Gold by and large is present in thiosulphidic state in these fluids. When these solutes meet an iron rich rock, formation of several types of sulphides such as pyrite, arsenopyrite, stibnite will take place and gold from sulphides will be released and deposited. Generation of such fluids generally takes place in a subduction zone complexes as large

volume of basaltic rocks which contain 5–10 ppb gold become available for remobilization and concentration of gold.

Conclusions

The available data shows that the gold concentrations in low grade gold deposits having a composite alteration envelop do not give consistent values and are highly dependent on initial distribution pattern, the size of the sample subjected for a particular type of analysis and type of analytical technique used. Furthermore, the accuracy becomes complicated with varying techniques because of the presence of refractory gold locked in different minerals. It is also found that gravity concentration by Knelson concentrator is not very efficient in low grade deposits hosted in basic volcanic rocks having coarse grained heavy minerals such as magnetite and ilmenite along with submicron size fine grained gold. As India's gold consumption exceeds production, there is a need in our country to search for advanced exploration and exploitation techniques to convert these low grade ores to gold mines.

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References

1. R. Kerrich, *Science*, 1999, **284**, 2101.
2. R. Kerrich and D. A. Wyman, *Mineralogy and Petrology*, 1993, **51**, 147.
3. R. Kerrich, R. Goldfarb, D. Groves and S. Garwin, *SEG Reviews*, 2000, **13**, 501.
4. K. Sreeramachandra Rao, *Geological Survey of India*, 2001, **58**, 11 (Special publication).
5. F. P. Bierlein, D. I. Groves, R. Goldfarb and B. Dube, *Mineralium Deposita*, 2006, **40**, 874.
6. S. M. Naqvi, Capital Publishing Company, New Delhi, 2005, p. 450.
7. C. Manikyamba and T. C. Khanna, *Gondwana Research*,

- 2007, **11**, 476.
8. D. I. Groves, R. J. Goldfarb, F. Robert and C. J. R. Hart, *Economic Geology*, 2003, **98**, 1.
 9. D. I. Groves, K. C. Condie, R. J. Goldfarb, J. M. A. Hronsky and R. M. Vielreicher, *Economic Geology*, 2005, **100**, 203.
 10. C. Manikyamba, S. M. Naqvi, R. H. Sawkar and G. R. Group, *Current Science*, 1997, **72**, 515.
 11. C. Manikyamba, S. M. Naqvi, M. Ram Mohan, T. Ganeswar Rao, *Ore Geology Reviews*, 2004a, **24**, 199.
 12. C. Manikyamba, Robert Kerrich, S. M. Naqvi and M. Rammohan, *Precambrian Research*, 2004b, **134**, 21.
 13. V. Balaram, R. Mathur, M. Satyanarayanan, S. S. Sawant, P. Roy, K. S. V. Subramanyam, C. T. Kamala, K. V. Anjiah, S. L. Ramesh and B. Dasaram, *Journal of Metrological Society of India*, 2012, **27**, 87.
 14. T. C. McCuaig and R. Kerrich, *Ore Geology Reviews*, 1998, **12**, 381.
 15. R. R. Loucks and J. A. Maurogenes, *Science*, 1999, **284**, 2159.